

Automatic Extraction of Behavioral Features for Test Program Similarity Analysis: Results Name Matches

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This document reports name matches for the experimental results in the paper: *Automatic Extraction of Behavioral Features for Test Program Similarity Analysis*.

Figure 7a.

Number on paper	Test Program Name
0	testAddMoney
1	testAddMoney1
2	testAddMoney2
3	testAdminQueryAll
4	testAdminQueryAll1
5	testCancelOrder1
6	testCheck
7	testCheckSecurityAboutOrder
8	testCollectTicket
9	testCreate1
10	testCreate2
11	testDelete
12	testDelete1
13	testDelete2
14	testDeleteConfig
15	testDeleteContacts
16	testDeleteFoodOrder
17	testDeleteOrder
18	testDeleteOrder1
19	testDeleteRoute
20	testDeleteTrain
21	testDeleteTravel
22	testDeleteTrip
23	testDeleteUser
24	testDrawBack
25	testDrawBack1
26	testDrawBack2
27	testExecuteTicket
28	testFindAllFoodOrder
29	testFindAllOrder
30	testFindAllSecurityConfig
31	testFindByConsignee
32	testFindById
33	testFindByRouteIdAndTrainType1
34	testFindFoodOrderById

35	testGetAllAssuranceType
36	testGetAllAssurances
37	testGetAllConfigs
38	testGetAllContacts
39	testGetAllFood
40	testGetAllFoodStores
41	testGetAllOrders
42	testGetAllPrices
43	testGetAllStations
44	testGetAllTrains
45	testGetAllTravels
46	testGetAllUser
47	testGetAllUsers
48	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds
49	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds2
50	testGetFoodStoresOfStation
51	testGetOrderById
52	testGetOrderById1
53	testGetOrderPrice
54	testGetOrderPrice1
55	testGetPriceConfig
56	testGetPriceInfo
57	testGetRouteById1
58	testGetRouteByTripId
59	testGetRouteByTripId1
60	testGetTrainFoodOfTrip
61	testGetTrainTypeByTripId
62	testGetTripByRoute2
63	testGetTripsByRouteId
64	testInitPayment1
65	testInitPayment2
66	testListFoodStoresByStationId2
67	testListTrainFoodByTripId2
68	testModifyAssurance
69	testModifyOrder
70	testModifyOrder1
71	testPay
72	testPay1
73	testPay2
74	testPayOrder
75	testPayOrder1
76	testQuery
77	testQuery1
78	testQuery2
79	testQueryAccount
80	testQueryAddMoney
81	testQueryAll
82	testQueryAll1
83	testQueryAlreadySoldOrders

84	testQueryByConsignee2
85	testQueryById
86	testQueryByStartAndTerminal
87	testQueryForStationId
88	testQueryOrdersForRefresh
89	testQueryPayment
90	testQueryPayment1
91	testRetrieve
92	testRetrieve1
93	testUpdate1
94	testUpdate2

Figure 7b.

Rows		Columns	
Number on paper	Test Program Name	Number on paper	Test Program Name
0	testAddMoney	0	testAddMoney
1	testAddMoney1	1	testAddMoney1
2	testAddMoney2	2	testAddMoney2
3	testAddNewSecurityConfig1	3	testAdminQueryAll
4	testAddNewSecurityConfig2	4	testAdminQueryAll1
5	testAdminQueryAll	5	testCancelOrder1
6	testAdminQueryAll1	6	testCheck
7	testCancelOrder1	7	testCheckSecurityAboutOrder
8	testCheck	8	testCollectTicket
9	testCheckSecurityAboutOrder	9	testCreate1
10	testCollectTicket	10	testCreate2
11	testCreate	11	testDelete
12	testCreate1	12	testDelete1
13	testCreate2	13	testDelete2
14	testCreateConfig	14	testDeleteConfig
15	testCreateContacts1	15	testDeleteContacts
16	testCreateContacts2	16	testDeleteFoodOrder
17	testCreateFoodOrder	17	testDeleteOrder
18	testCreateFoodOrder1	18	testDeleteOrder1
19	testCreateFoodStore1	19	testDeleteRoute
20	testCreateFoodStore2	20	testDeleteTrain
21	testCreateNewContacts	21	testDeleteTravel
22	testCreateNewContactsAdmin	22	testDeleteTrip
23	testCreateNewPriceConfig1	23	testDeleteUser
24	testCreateTrainFood1	24	testDrawBack
25	testCreateTrainFood2	25	testDrawBack1
26	testDelete	26	testDrawBack2
27	testDelete1	27	testExecuteTicket
28	testDelete2	28	testFindAllFoodOrder
29	testDeleteConfig	29	testFindAllFoodOrder1
30	testDeleteContacts	30	testFindAllOrder

31	testDeleteFoodOrder	31	testFindAllPriceConfig2
32	testDeleteOrder	32	testFindAllSecurityConfig
33	testDeleteOrder1	33	testFindAllSecurityConfig1
34	testDeletePriceConfig1	34	testFindByConsignee
35	testDeletePriceConfig2	35	testFindById
36	testDeleteRoute	36	testFindByRouteIdAndTrainType1
37	testDeleteRoute2	37	testFindFoodOrderByOrderId
38	testDeleteTrain	38	testGetAllAssuranceType
39	testDeleteTravel	39	testGetAllAssurances
40	testDeleteTrip	40	testGetAllConfigs
41	testDeleteUser	41	testGetAllContacts
42	testDrawBack	42	testGetAllContacts1
43	testDrawBack1	43	testGetAllFood
44	testDrawBack2	44	testGetAllFoodStores
45	testExecuteTicket	45	testGetAllOrders
46	testFindAllFoodOrder	46	testGetAllPrices
47	testFindAllOrder	47	testGetAllRoutes1
48	testFindAllSecurityConfig	48	testGetAllStations
49	testFindByConsignee	49	testGetAllTrains
50	testFindById	50	testGetAllTravels
51	testFindByRouteIdAndTrainType1	51	testGetAllUser
52	testFindByRouteIdAndTrainType2	52	testGetAllUsers
53	testFindFoodOrderByOrderId	53	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds
54	testGetAllAssuranceType	54	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds2
55	testGetAllAssurances	55	testGetFoodStoresOfStation
56	testGetAllConfigs	56	testGetOrderById
57	testGetAllContacts	57	testGetOrderById1
58	testGetAllFood	58	testGetOrderPrice
59	testGetAllFoodStores	59	testGetOrderPrice1
60	testGetAllOrders	60	testGetPriceConfig
61	testGetAllPrices	61	testGetPriceInfo
62	testGetAllStations	62	testGetRouteById1
63	testGetAllTrains	63	testGetRouteByTripId
64	testGetAllTravels	64	testGetRouteByTripId1
65	testGetAllUser	65	testGetTrainFoodOfTrip
66	testGetAllUsers	66	testGetTrainTypeByTripId
67	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds	67	testGetTripByRoute2
68	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds1	68	testGetTripsByRouteId
69	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds2	69	testInitPayment1
70	testGetFoodStoresOfStation	70	testInitPayment2
71	testGetOrderById	71	testListFoodStores1
72	testGetOrderById1	72	testListFoodStoresByStationId2
73	testGetOrderPrice	73	testListTrainFood1
74	testGetOrderPrice1	74	testListTrainFoodByTripId2
75	testGetPriceConfig	75	testModifyAssurance
76	testGetPriceInfo	76	testModifyOrder
77	testGetRouteById1	77	testModifyOrder1
78	testGetRouteById2	78	testPay
79	testGetRouteByTripId	79	testPay1

80	testGetRouteByTripId1	80	testPay2
81	testGetRouteByTripId2	81	testPayOrder
82	testGetTrainFoodOfTrip	82	testPayOrder1
83	testGetTrainTypeByTripId	83	testQuery
84	testGetTripByRoute2	84	testQuery1
85	testGetTripsByRouteId	85	testQuery2
86	testInitPayment1	86	testQueryAccount
87	testInitPayment2	87	testQueryAddMoney
88	testListFoodStoresByStationId1	88	testQueryAll
89	testListFoodStoresByStationId2	89	testQueryAll1
90	testListTrainFoodByTripId1	90	testQueryAlreadySoldOrders
91	testListTrainFoodByTripId2	91	testQueryByConsignee2
92	testModifyAssurance	92	testQueryById
93	testModifyContacts	93	testQueryByStartAndTerminal
94	testModifyOrder	94	testQueryForStationId
95	testModifyOrder1	95	testQueryInfo1
96	testModifyPriceConfig	96	testQueryOrdersForRefresh
97	testModifySecurityConfig1	97	testQueryPayment
98	testModifySecurityConfig2	98	testQueryPayment1
99	testPay	99	testRetrieve
100	testPay1	100	testRetrieve1
101	testPay2	101	testUpdate1
102	testPayOrder	102	testUpdate2
103	testPayOrder1		
104	testQuery		
105	testQuery1		
106	testQuery2		
107	testQueryAccount		
108	testQueryAddMoney		
109	testQueryAll		
110	testQueryAll1		
111	testQueryAlreadySoldOrders		
112	testQueryByConsignee2		
113	testQueryById		
114	testQueryByStartAndTerminal		
115	testQueryForStationId		
116	testQueryOrdersForRefresh		
117	testQueryPayment		
118	testQueryPayment1		
119	testRetrieve		
120	testRetrieve1		
121	testSaveUser		
122	testUpdate		
123	testUpdate1		
124	testUpdate2		
125	testUpdateConfig		
126	testUpdateFoodOrder		
127	testUpdateFoodOrder1		
128	testUpdatePriceConfig1		

Figure 7c.

Number on paper	Test Program Name
0	testAddConfig
1	testAddContact
2	testAddContacts
3	testAddCreateNewOrder
4	testAddMoney
5	testAddMoney1
6	testAddMoney2
7	testAddNewOrder1
8	testAddNewOrder2
9	testAddNewSecurityConfig1
10	testAddNewSecurityConfig2
11	testAddOrder
12	testAddOrder1
13	testAddOrder2
14	testAddPrice
15	testAddRoute
16	testAddStation
17	testAddTrain
18	testAddTravel
19	testAddTravel1
20	testAddTravel2
21	testAddTravel3
22	testAddTravel4
23	testAddUser
24	testAdminQueryAll
25	testAdminQueryAll1
26	testAlterOrder1
27	testCancelOrder1
28	testCancelOrder2
29	testCheck
30	testCheckSecurityAboutOrder
31	testCheckStationExists
32	testCollectTicket
33	testCreate
34	testCreate1
35	testCreate2
36	testCreateAccount
37	testCreateAccount1
38	testCreateAccount2
39	testCreateAndModify1
40	testCreateAndModify2
41	testCreateAndModify3
42	testCreateAndModifyRoute
43	testCreateConfig

44	testCreateContacts1
45	testCreateContacts2
46	testCreateFoodOrder
47	testCreateFoodOrder1
48	testCreateFoodStore1
49	testCreateFoodStore2
50	testCreateNewAssurance
51	testCreateNewContacts
52	testCreateNewContactsAdmin
53	testCreateNewOrder
54	testCreateNewPriceConfig1
55	testCreateTrainFood1
56	testCreateTrainFood2
57	testCreateTrip
58	testDelete
59	testDelete1
60	testDelete2
61	testDeleteConfig
62	testDeleteContact
63	testDeleteContacts
64	testDeleteFoodOrder
65	testDeleteOrder
66	testDeleteOrder1
67	testDeleteOrder2
68	testDeletePrice
69	testDeletePriceConfig1
70	testDeletePriceConfig2
71	testDeleteRoute
72	testDeleteRoute1
73	testDeleteRoute2
74	testDeleteStation
75	testDeleteTrain
76	testDeleteTravel
77	testDeleteTravel1
78	testDeleteTravel2
79	testDeleteTrip
80	testDeleteUser
81	testDipatchSeat
82	testDistributeSeat1
83	testDistributeSeat2
84	testDrawBack
85	testDrawBack1
86	testDrawBack2
87	testExecuteTicket
88	testFindAllFoodOrder
89	testFindAllFoodOrder1
90	testFindAllOrder
91	testFindAllPriceConfig2
92	testFindAllSecurityConfig

93	testFindAllSecurityConfig1
94	testFindByConsignee
95	testFindById
96	testFindByRouteIdAndTrainType1
97	testFindByRouteIdAndTrainType2
98	testFindFoodOrderByOrderId
99	testGetAccount
100	testGetAllAssuranceType
101	testGetAllAssuranceTypes
102	testGetAllAssurances
103	testGetAllAssurances1
104	testGetAllConfigs
105	testGetAllContacts
106	testGetAllContacts1
107	testGetAllFood
108	testGetAllFoodStores
109	testGetAllOrders
110	testGetAllOrders1
111	testGetAllOrders2
112	testGetAllPrices
113	testGetAllRoutes
114	testGetAllRoutes1
115	testGetAllStations
116	testGetAllTrains
117	testGetAllTravels
118	testGetAllTravels1
119	testGetAllTravels2
120	testGetAllUser
121	testGetAllUsers
122	testGetByCheapest
123	testGetByMinStation
124	testGetByQuickest
125	testGetCheapest
126	testGetCheapestRoutes
127	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds
128	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds1
129	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds2
130	testGetFoodStoresOfStation
131	testGetLeftTicketOfInterva2
132	testGetLeftTicketOfInterval
133	testGetMinStation
134	testGetMinStopStations
135	testGetOrderById
136	testGetOrderById1
137	testGetOrderById2
138	testGetOrderPrice
139	testGetOrderPrice1
140	testGetOrderPrice2
141	testGetPriceByWeightAndRegion

142	testGetPriceConfig
143	testGetPriceInfo
144	testGetQuickest
145	testGetQuickestRoutes
146	testGetRouteById1
147	testGetRouteById2
148	testGetRouteByTripId
149	testGetRouteByTripId1
150	testGetRouteByTripId2
151	testGetSoldTickets1
152	testGetSoldTickets2
153	testGetTicketListByDateAndTripId
154	testGetToken1
155	testGetToken2
156	testGetTrainFoodOfTrip
157	testGetTrainTypeByTripId
158	testGetTransferResult
159	testGetTransferSearch
160	testGetTripAllDetailInfo
161	testGetTripByRoute2
162	testGetTripsByRouteId
163	testHome
164	testInitOrder1
165	testInitOrder2
166	testInitPayment1
167	testInitPayment2
168	testInsertConsign
169	testListFoodStores1
170	testListFoodStoresByStationId1
171	testListFoodStoresByStationId2
172	testListTrainFood1
173	testListTrainFoodByTripId1
174	testListTrainFoodByTripId2
175	testModifyAssurance
176	testModifyConfig
177	testModifyContact
178	testModifyContacts
179	testModifyOrder
180	testModifyOrder1
181	testModifyOrder2
182	testModifyPrice
183	testModifyPriceConfig
184	testModifySecurityConfig1
185	testModifySecurityConfig2
186	testModifyStation
187	testModifyTrain
188	testOrderCancelSuccess
189	testOrderChangedSuccess
190	testOrderCreateSuccess

191	testPay
192	testPay1
193	testPay2
194	testPayDifference
195	testPayOrder
196	testPayOrder1
197	testPayOrder2
198	testPreserve
199	testPreserveSuccess
200	testQuery
201	testQuery1
202	testQuery2
203	testQueryAccount
204	testQueryAddMoney
205	testQueryAddMoney1
206	testQueryAll
207	testQueryAll1
208	testQueryAlreadySoldOrders
209	testQueryByConsignee1
210	testQueryByConsignee2
211	testQueryById
212	testQueryByStartAndTerminal
213	testQueryForStationId
214	testQueryForTravel
215	testQueryInfo1
216	testQueryInfo2
217	testQueryOrders
218	testQueryOrdersForRefresh
219	testQueryPayment
220	testQueryPayment1
221	testQueryTrainType
222	testRebook
223	testRetrieve
224	testRetrieve1
225	testRetrieve2
226	testSaveChanges1
227	testSaveChanges2
228	testSaveOrderInfo
229	testSaveUser
230	testSearchMinStopStations
231	testSearchQuickestResult
232	testSendEmail
233	testTicketCollect1
234	testTicketCollect2
235	testTicketExecute1
236	testTicketExecute2
237	testUpdate
238	testUpdate1
239	testUpdate2

240	testUpdateConfig
241	testUpdateConsign
242	testUpdateFoodOrder
243	testUpdateFoodOrder1
244	testUpdateOrder
245	testUpdateOrder1
246	testUpdateOrder2
247	testUpdatePriceConfig1
248	testUpdatePriceConfig2
249	testUpdateTravel
250	testUpdateTravel1
251	testUpdateTravel2
252	testUpdateTrip
253	testUpdateUser

Figure 8a.

Number on paper	Test Program Name
0	testAddMoney
1	testAddMoney1
2	testAddMoney2
3	testAdminQueryAll
4	testAdminQueryAll1
5	testCancelOrder1
6	testCheck
7	testCheckSecurityAboutOrder
8	testCollectTicket
9	testCreate1
10	testCreate2
11	testDelete
12	testDelete1
13	testDelete2
14	testDeleteConfig
15	testDeleteContacts
16	testDeleteFoodOrder
17	testDeleteOrder
18	testDeleteOrder1
19	testDeleteRoute
20	testDeleteTrain
21	testDeleteTravel
22	testDeleteTrip
23	testDeleteUser
24	testDrawBack
25	testDrawBack1
26	testDrawBack2
27	testExecuteTicket
28	testFindAllFoodOrder
29	testFindAllFoodOrder1
30	testFindAllOrder

31	testFindAllPriceConfig2
32	testFindAllSecurityConfig
33	testFindAllSecurityConfig1
34	testFindByConsignee
35	testFindById
36	testFindByRouteIdAndTrainType1
37	testFindFoodOrderByOrderId
38	testGetAllAssuranceType
39	testGetAllAssurances
40	testGetAllConfigs
41	testGetAllContacts
42	testGetAllContacts1
43	testGetAllFood
44	testGetAllFoodStores
45	testGetAllOrders
46	testGetAllPrices
47	testGetAllRoutes1
48	testGetAllStations
49	testGetAllTrains
50	testGetAllTravels
51	testGetAllUser
52	testGetAllUsers
53	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds
54	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds2
55	testGetFoodStoresOfStation
56	testGetOrderById
57	testGetOrderById1
58	testGetOrderPrice
59	testGetOrderPrice1
60	testGetPriceConfig
61	testGetPriceInfo
62	testGetRouteById1
63	testGetRouteByTripId
64	testGetRouteByTripId1
65	testGetTrainFoodOfTrip
66	testGetTrainTypeByTripId
67	testGetTripByRoute2
68	testGetTripsByRouteId
69	testInitPayment1
70	testInitPayment2
71	testListFoodStores1
72	testListFoodStoresByStationId2
73	testListTrainFood1
74	testListTrainFoodByTripId2
75	testModifyAssurance
76	testModifyOrder
77	testModifyOrder1
78	testPay
79	testPay1

80	testPay2
81	testPayOrder
82	testPayOrder1
83	testQuery
84	testQuery1
85	testQuery2
86	testQueryAccount
87	testQueryAddMoney
88	testQueryAll
89	testQueryAll1
90	testQueryAlreadySoldOrders
91	testQueryByConsignee2
92	testQueryById
93	testQueryByStartAndTerminal
94	testQueryForStationId
95	testQueryInfo1
96	testQueryOrdersForRefresh
97	testQueryPayment
98	testQueryPayment1
99	testRetrieve
100	testRetrieve1
101	testUpdate1
102	testUpdate2

Figure 8b.

Number on paper	Test Program Name
0	testAddConfig
1	testAddContact
2	testAddContacts
3	testAddCreateNewOrder
4	testAddMoney
5	testAddMoney1
6	testAddMoney2
7	testAddNewOrder1
8	testAddNewOrder2
9	testAddNewSecurityConfig1
10	testAddNewSecurityConfig2
11	testAddOrder
12	testAddOrder1
13	testAddOrder2
14	testAddPrice
15	testAddRoute
16	testAddStation
17	testAddTrain
18	testAddTravel
19	testAddTravel1
20	testAddTravel2
21	testAddTravel3

22	testAddTravel4
23	testAddUser
24	testAdminQueryAll
25	testAdminQueryAll1
26	testAlterOrder1
27	testCancelOrder1
28	testCancelOrder2
29	testCheck
30	testCheckSecurityAboutOrder
31	testCheckStationExists
32	testCollectTicket
33	testCreate
34	testCreate1
35	testCreate2
36	testCreateAccount
37	testCreateAccount1
38	testCreateAccount2
39	testCreateAndModify1
40	testCreateAndModify2
41	testCreateAndModify3
42	testCreateAndModifyRoute
43	testCreateConfig
44	testCreateContacts1
45	testCreateContacts2
46	testCreateFoodOrder
47	testCreateFoodOrder1
48	testCreateFoodStore1
49	testCreateFoodStore2
50	testCreateNewAssurance
51	testCreateNewContacts
52	testCreateNewContactsAdmin
53	testCreateNewOrder
54	testCreateNewPriceConfig1
55	testCreateTrainFood1
56	testCreateTrainFood2
57	testCreateTrip
58	testDelete
59	testDelete1
60	testDelete2
61	testDeleteConfig
62	testDeleteContact
63	testDeleteContacts
64	testDeleteFoodOrder
65	testDeleteOrder
66	testDeleteOrder1
67	testDeleteOrder2
68	testDeletePrice
69	testDeletePriceConfig1
70	testDeletePriceConfig2

71	testDeleteRoute
72	testDeleteRoute1
73	testDeleteRoute2
74	testDeleteStation
75	testDeleteTrain
76	testDeleteTravel
77	testDeleteTravel1
78	testDeleteTravel2
79	testDeleteTrip
80	testDeleteUser
81	testDipatchSeat
82	testDistributeSeat1
83	testDistributeSeat2
84	testDrawBack
85	testDrawBack1
86	testDrawBack2
87	testExecuteTicket
88	testFindAllFoodOrder
89	testFindAllFoodOrder1
90	testFindAllOrder
91	testFindAllPriceConfig2
92	testFindAllSecurityConfig
93	testFindAllSecurityConfig1
94	testFindByConsignee
95	testFindById
96	testFindByRouteIdAndTrainType1
97	testFindByRouteIdAndTrainType2
98	testFindFoodOrderByOrderId
99	testGetAccount
100	testGetAllAssuranceType
101	testGetAllAssuranceTypes
102	testGetAllAssurances
103	testGetAllAssurances1
104	testGetAllConfigs
105	testGetAllContacts
106	testGetAllContacts1
107	testGetAllFood
108	testGetAllFoodStores
109	testGetAllOrders
110	testGetAllOrders1
111	testGetAllOrders2
112	testGetAllPrices
113	testGetAllRoutes
114	testGetAllRoutes1
115	testGetAllStations
116	testGetAllTrains
117	testGetAllTravels
118	testGetAllTravels1
119	testGetAllTravels2

120	testGetAllUser
121	testGetAllUsers
122	testGetByCheapest
123	testGetByMinStation
124	testGetByQuickest
125	testGetCheapest
126	testGetCheapestRoutes
127	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds
128	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds1
129	testGetFoodStoresByStationIds2
130	testGetFoodStoresOfStation
131	testGetLeftTicketOfInterva2
132	testGetLeftTicketOfInterval
133	testGetMinStation
134	testGetMinStopStations
135	testGetOrderById
136	testGetOrderById1
137	testGetOrderById2
138	testGetOrderPrice
139	testGetOrderPrice1
140	testGetOrderPrice2
141	testGetPriceByWeightAndRegion
142	testGetPriceConfig
143	testGetPriceInfo
144	testGetQuickest
145	testGetQuickestRoutes
146	testGetRouteById1
147	testGetRouteById2
148	testGetRouteByTripId
149	testGetRouteByTripId1
150	testGetRouteByTripId2
151	testGetSoldTickets1
152	testGetSoldTickets2
153	testGetTicketListByDateAndTripId
154	testGetToken1
155	testGetToken2
156	testGetTrainFoodOfTrip
157	testGetTrainTypeByTripId
158	testGetTransferResult
159	testGetTransferSearch
160	testGetTripAllDetailInfo
161	testGetTripByRoute2
162	testGetTripsByRouteId
163	testHome
164	testInitOrder1
165	testInitOrder2
166	testInitPayment1
167	testInitPayment2
168	testInsertConsign

169	testListFoodStores1
170	testListFoodStoresByStationId1
171	testListFoodStoresByStationId2
172	testListTrainFood1
173	testListTrainFoodByTripId1
174	testListTrainFoodByTripId2
175	testModifyAssurance
176	testModifyConfig
177	testModifyContact
178	testModifyContacts
179	testModifyOrder
180	testModifyOrder1
181	testModifyOrder2
182	testModifyPrice
183	testModifyPriceConfig
184	testModifySecurityConfig1
185	testModifySecurityConfig2
186	testModifyStation
187	testModifyTrain
188	testOrderCancelSuccess
189	testOrderChangedSuccess
190	testOrderCreateSuccess
191	testPay
192	testPay1
193	testPay2
194	testPayDifference
195	testPayOrder
196	testPayOrder1
197	testPayOrder2
198	testPreserve
199	testPreserveSuccess
200	testQuery
201	testQuery1
202	testQuery2
203	testQueryAccount
204	testQueryAddMoney
205	testQueryAddMoney1
206	testQueryAll
207	testQueryAll1
208	testQueryAlreadySoldOrders
209	testQueryByConsignee1
210	testQueryByConsignee2
211	testQueryById
212	testQueryByStartAndTerminal
213	testQueryForStationId
214	testQueryForTravel
215	testQueryInfo1
216	testQueryInfo2
217	testQueryOrders

218	testQueryOrdersForRefresh
219	testQueryPayment
220	testQueryPayment1
221	testQueryTrainType
222	testRebook
223	testRetrieve
224	testRetrieve1
225	testRetrieve2
226	testSaveChanges1
227	testSaveChanges2
228	testSaveOrderInfo
229	testSaveUser
230	testSearchMinStopStations
231	testSearchQuickestResult
232	testSendEmail
233	testTicketCollect1
234	testTicketCollect2
235	testTicketExecute1
236	testTicketExecute2
237	testUpdate
238	testUpdate1
239	testUpdate2
240	testUpdateConfig
241	testUpdateConsign
242	testUpdateFoodOrder
243	testUpdateFoodOrder1
244	testUpdateOrder
245	testUpdateOrder1
246	testUpdateOrder2
247	testUpdatePriceConfig1
248	testUpdatePriceConfig2
249	testUpdateTravel
250	testUpdateTravel1
251	testUpdateTravel2
252	testUpdateTrip
253	testUpdateUser